

D2.7 Technical Documentation of R3: Planning Module

WP2 Development of Computed Assisted Waste Management Systems

FDEUSTO
Report
Public

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CEP	Complex Event Processing
D2D	Door to door
EA	Evolutionary Algorithms
EWC	European Waste Catalogue
GE.R.A	Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività
GSS	GeoSmartSim
GUI	Graphic User Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance indicator
MAS	Multi-Agent System
PAYT	Pay as you throw
RFID	Radio-frequency identification

Glossary

Concept	Definition
GeoSmartSim	Smart Simulation Engine
GE.R.A	It is the Italian acronym for “Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività”, which means “Resources and Activities Management”

1. Introduction

In this deliverable we provide the technical description of the R3: Planning Module. This module will consist of several components that will help waste managers improve the planning of the system. Section 2 will provide a broad description of all the components of R2 and its relations with the rest of solutions developed in the Waste4Think. Section 3 covers the GE.R.A. system, a Mid Term Planning module. Section 4 will cover the Long-Term Planning model. Section 5 will be devoted to the Green Procurement tool and, Section 6 will present the Zero Waste Ecosystem/Events Planner, Section 7 will present the Social Actions Module, and finally, Section 8 will focus on the Invoicing Module.

Please note that this document only provides the technical description of R3: Planning Module, the status of the development can be read in **the Monitoring Action Reports (D1.4 to D1.7)**.

2. Relation with the rest of components

The Planning Module (R3) is the software module of Waste4Think devoted to help urban planners and waste collection companies in the planning of the Waste Management System. It consists of four different tools:

- **Planning Tools:** these are the central tools of the module. It is composed of two sub-tools:
 - **Mid Term Planning Tool:** This tool will help with the mid-term planning of the human resources, vehicles, equipment resources, and collection routes (weeks to month ahead). Sections 3 will present the details of this tool.
 - **Long Term Planning Tool:** This tool will help with the long-term planning of the waste management system (years ahead). Sections 4 contains the details of this tool.
- **Green Procurement:** this tool will help in the writing and evaluation of green procurements. Section 5 is devoted to this tool.
- **Zero Waste Ecosystem planner:** this tool allows the planning and monitoring of Zero Waste events and Ecosystems. Section 6 contains the details of this tool.
- **Social Action planner:** this tool allows to plan and monitor a Social Action Strategy. Section 7 covers the details of this tool.
- **Invoicing module:** this tool will allow to holistically assess the impact that the introduction of innovative economic instruments (PAYT) will have. Section 8 details this tool. Please note that this tool only covers the simulation of the impact of introducing new economic instruments and not the management of them (invoice generation, management, etc.). This will be covered in detail in Deliverable D5.1.

Figure 1. Relation of the architecture of R3 with the overall architecture of Waste4Think.

Figure 1 shows the relations of these components (in blue) with the rest of eco-solutions of Waste4Think. As can be seen, R1 and R3 are highly interconnected:

- first, the information that the previous tools needs comes from the different components of R1 (the Context Broker and the Persistence layer),
- moreover, the models used to perform several of the operations will be deployed in the Complex Event Processing (CEP) engine, and

- finally, some of the tools of R3 will be accessible through the W4T-core component of R1, specifically, the Green Procurement, the Zero Waste Ecosystem/Event planner and the Invoice Module. Finally, the visualization of the results will use the Dashboard (R1).

Another important aspect to mention is the integration between the Serious Games and the Long-Term Planner as it will be used in the Planning Game as a source of information.

The main use cases for these tools are A1 and A16, but are also related to C5, C13 and S10 (see Deliverable D1.1). The list of functional requirements fulfilled by the components of R3 are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Functional Requirement fulfilled by the components of R3.

ID	FR	Mid-Term	Long-Term Planning	Green Procurement	Zero-Waste Ecosystems/	Social Actions planner	Invoicing
R3_FR1	To support the long-term planning	X	X				
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models		X				
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios		X				
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution		X				
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity		X				
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants		X				
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems	X	X				
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)		X				
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots	X	X				
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campaigns		X		X		
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)	X	X				X
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system	X	X				
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination of collection system plus treatment plans		X				
R3_FR1.3.2	Simulate the localization and size of the collection points and treatment plans	X	X				
R3_FR1.3.3	Simulate combinations of prevention campaigns					X	
R3_FR1.3.4	Take into consideration multiple criteria (economical, environmental and social impacts)		X				
R3_FR1.3.5	Simulate different transport means for waste collection		X				
R3_FR1.3.6	Simulate the effect of different combination of economic instruments						X
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events				X		
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements			X			
R3_FR1.5.1	To identify criteria for the tendering			X			
R3_FR1.5.2	To evaluate the applicants of the tender			X			

2.1. User Stories – Long-Term Planning

Bilbao is growing. A complete new neighbourhood for more than 20000 persons is being planned in the Zorrozaurre island. Emilio oversees planning the waste management system there. This is an overwhelming task due to the huge amount of decisions he must take so he seeks for help and starts using the Long-Term Planning Module.

First, Emilio has to create a what-if scenario. For this end, he needs to retrieve the geographical information from the municipal GIS (roads and buildings footprints mainly) and some projections on both the temporal and spatial distribution of the population that is going to live there. Emilio use the tools available in the Long-Term Planning module to check the information provided and makes some minor adjustments to the baseline scenario guided by the interface. When he is happy with the result, Emilio starts performing several simulations.

First, he wants to compare the sustainability of a D2D collection against a Bin collection. For that, he manually adds a series of collection points to the baseline scenario and performs a simulation to calculate the impact of the traditional system. He is not sure whether he has placed the collection points in the best places, so Emilio uses the optimization module to improve the localization of the collection points. Then, he runs the simulation to compare. Finally, he removes the collection points, selects a D2D collection system and performs a simulation. Now he has the results of the three what-if scenarios. Of the three scenarios, the one that achieved the best numeric results was that of the optimized collection system based on bins. Emilio will continue the planning assuming this.

Now, Emilio wants to know how many vehicles and routes he needs to collect the waste in the Island. To this end, he designs some routes using the editor and performs a simulation. He is not very satisfied with the results and tries the optimization module. In this case, the optimization module has not been able to improve the scenario provided by Emilio. Seems like the collection route designed by him was already very good.

Finally, Emilio wants to decide if he can introduce some prevention actions and in situ treatment plants. For that, he will also use the Long-Term Planning module. He introduces the results of the previous simulations in the tool and locates the potential points where the treatments plants could be located. First, he selects a couple of treatments he believes adequate and performs a couple of simulations with different combinations. He is satisfied with one that contains a local composting plan and a small incinerator, but he wants to see if the optimization module could provide a better scenario. Emilio selects the potential treatment plants that he wants to consider, and the system finds a different solution involving a FORBI production and a nappies treatment plan.

Now he is satisfied with all the findings and thinks he can start writing the plan to present to the mayor.

2.2. User Stories – Mid-term planning G.E.R.A.

Giuseppe lives in Italy and he is responsible for the “Collection and transport of urban waste, urban hygiene, separate waste collection and CCR management” Sector Company that furnishes several environmental services. In fact, the company has other Sectors, such as “collection and transport of special waste”, “environmental remediation and securing, demolition work and construction and maintenance”, “waste storage and treatment plant”, “renewable energy and energy efficiency” and “wind farms”.

Obviously, the same operators, as well as trucks and equipment can be used from different sectors and sometimes these sectors work together for the same Municipality or Private Customer.

The challenges for Giuseppe

In order to furnish these services, Giuseppe needs to:

- Respect the contractual obligations for the provision of urban waste collection and hygiene services.
- Optimize the resources available for these services (men, vehicles, equipment) in order to saturate and increase efficiency.
- Correctly manage the information on the provision of services (hours, km) to verify the compliance with the estimated costs for the execution of these services.
- Correctly manage the duties related to operators in terms of training, health and safety.
- Correctly manage the tasks related to the vehicles in terms of maintenance, mandatory periodic checks, checks by Public Bodies.

- Have data to be processed and analysed in order to verify the economic and financial performance of the services.
- Facilitate the service management processes for the individual company functions through automated and centralized procedures.

Giuseppe has to start a new collection service; he wants to be sure that he is correctly planning everything that his company needs to do for the Municipality, so he has two choices:

1. One option is to do this work on his own, using his knowledge and his excel file, without connection to the Company' management software and considering that this general software for the management of the personal does not consider the equipment and vehicles management and cannot automatically plan activities. In fact, Giuseppe's Company, as well as many Italian Waste Collection Companies or Companies that in general are active in the environmental field, is not provided with advanced IT systems for activities' management, control, planning and accounting.
2. Another option is related to the fact that Giuseppe have been informed by his furniture company that a new software is now implemented through the project "Waste4Think" (or by an intensive campaign of dissemination of the results that sent communications to all Waste Collection Companies). This software is called GE.R.A. and aims to provide the automatic planning of the services

Solving challenges with Waste4Think

Giuseppe chooses to use GE.R.A. and to evaluate its potentiality. He asks for his account ID. Every operator in the company will have its own account ID with a different set of restrictions according to their role. Because Giuseppe is a manager of the planning service for the door-to-door waste collection service, he asks the Personnel Sector to fill in the personal data of the operators since, without these data, it is not possible to view and manage any "operators" in GE.R.A..

Therefore, the Personnel Sector fills in:

- a) Human resource data:
- b) Personal data (name, surname, fiscal code, birth date, birth location, residence address, telephone number, etc).
- c) Agreements: ID agreement, ID operator, sector, assumption date, expire date, type of contract (referred to national level), number of hours to do etc.
- d) Driving licenses: ID driving license, license category, realised by, released date, expiration date.
- e) Tasks: tasks that can be done by each operator.
- f) Training: census on safety training for a specific task, safety trainings already done and the validity period for each one.

For example, the responsible of the Personnel Sector fills in on GE.R.A. the personal data of Mr Giovanni Rossi, who was born in Trento in 23/9/1965 and lives in Milan at Viale dei Tramonti, 99. His Fiscal Code is RSSGVN65I23L378S and he is a driver of a truck with compactor. Giovanni's National Labour Contract is about "environmental hygiene" category and it is of third level B. This driver can also perform minor operator tasks.

On the other hand, the Park Vehicles/Equipment Sector is responsible for the compilation of the software that regards to:

1. Vehicles and equipment/materials data:
 - a) Vehicle resources: id vehicle, type of vehicle, ID fleet vehicle, sector to which the vehicle can be used, licence plate, if the vehicle is active or not, ID operator (link between the vehicle and everyone can drive it), collection activity (which kind of specific activity can do the vehicle), the volume that the vehicle can managed, purchase date, vehicle value, fuel type, motor oil type, euro homologations, if the vehicle has GPS inside, etc....

- b) Equipment resources: ID equipment resources, equipment type, equipment category, description of the equipment, sector, serial number, license plate,
2. Examples of vehicles and equipment/materials used by “Collection and transport of urban waste, urban hygiene, separate waste collection and CCR management”:
 - a) Truck with compacting or single tank equipment; lift car to transport demountable containers from the ecological island; trucks with dump trucks and cranes;
 - b) Brush cutter, pressure washer, vacuum cleaners, drill, etc.
 - c) Example of construction material: barriers, scaffolding, wooden boards, signs, etc.

Finally, Giuseppe fills in information about:

3. Orders: that is the waste collection and urban hygiene in Seveso Municipality.
 - a) Services: a group of services composes an order. In this case, the services are:
 - i. door to door services for each kind of waste fraction and for both domestic and not-domestic users;
 - ii. manage the household waste centre;
 - iii. road sweeping services (mechanics type);
 - iv. Road sweeping/cleaning services (manual type);
 - v. Waste transport to final destination plants.
4. Activities: the service represents the set of activities to be done in the area of the Municipality. The activities are linked to the single service.
 - a) For the door to door collection, Giovanni sets the following activities:
 - i. drive a vehicle;
 - ii. waste collection (emptying containers).
 - b) For manage the household waste centre, Giovanni sets the activities:
 - iii. supervision by staff of the centre;
 - iv. drive the vehicles for transporting waste to final destinations;
 - c) For the road sweeping service, the set activities are:
 - i. drive vehicle;
 - ii. operator to support on road the service.
 - d) For the road sweeping/cleaning service, Giovanni set:
 - i. drive vehicle activity;
 - ii. manual cleaning activity;
5. For the waste transport to final destination plants:
 - i. the activity is drive the vehicle

For each service of the Order, Giuseppe must fill in:

- Frequency of the specific activity. Giuseppe sets up the system for the door to door collection of the organic waste, knowing by the contract between the parties that this service must be done three times a week: Monday, Wednesday and Friday.
- The zone in which the service is planned: Giuseppe navigates to the section of GE.R.A. where it is possible to choose the geographical zone of the Municipality and link each zone to a frequency of the specific activity and then the type of waste involved. Giuseppe links the frequency to the Old Town area of Seveso. Each zone has a different frequency of waste collection and needs different human resources, vehicle and equipment.
- The type of waste (EWC): organic waste - for the door-to-door collection in the Old Town Area.

These settings are defined in the contract between the Giuseppe' Company and the Municipality.

Finally, Giuseppe generates the calendar of the planned activities filling the referred period to be planned (from 1st January to 30th June) through GE.R.A.

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Based on the frequency information given by Giuseppe, the calendar shows every Monday, Wednesday and Friday of the set period. For each day of the generated calendar, the software generates the work shift: men, vehicles and equipment resources for that service.

Giuseppe views a table section which shows him the services for each day of the period and which men, vehicles and equipment GE.R.A. are assigned to the daily service.

Giuseppe sets up in the GE.R.A. software all the types of services he must provide and for each of them, sets the delivery frequencies, the areas in which they are to be carried out and the standard resources to be used for that specific service.

Services	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE EST	Orario Nominativo Targa 12.00-18.00 VITA CATALDO EM112PE	Orario Nominativo Targa	Orario Nominativo
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE NORD	Orario Nominativo Targa 12.00-18.00 VITA CATALDO EM112PE	Orario Nominativo Targa	Orario Nominativo
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE OVEST	Orario Nominativo Targa 12.00-18.00 VITA CATALDO EM112PE	Orario Nominativo Targa	Orario Nominativo

Operatori	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
PEREZ ANGELO BRUNO PIETRO PRETE ALFONSO DAI GIANFRANCO PICCIONE SANTO	VITA CATALDO PEREZ ANGELO BRUNO PIETRO PRETE ALFONSO DAI GIANFRANCO	VITA CATALDO PEREZ ANGELO BRUNO PIETRO PRETE ALFONSO DAI GIANFRANCO	

Automezzi	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	

Attrezzature	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
CSA 199 CSA 199 CSA 199 CSA 199 CSA 199	SALDATRICE AD ARCO TELWIN MOD. 188 MPI SALDATRICE AD ARCO TELWIN MOD. 188 MPI	SALDATRICE AD ARCO TELWIN MOD. 188 MPI SALDATRICE AD ARCO TELWIN MOD. 188 MPI	

He launches the planner, and this generates all the services to be done, distinct by day, and the resources allocated for each individual service (men, vehicles, equipment).

Giuseppe considers also the vehicles and equipment under arrest for maintenance before inserting the unavailable personal resources on holidays or illness.

The staff, thus, by using the software sees day by day, based on a planning with an annual view, the days in which the operators work and to which services they have been assigned.

Giuseppe has the final data on the provision of services (km, daytime, etc.) that his operators report at the end of the shift.

Thanks to GE.R.A., Giuseppe can verify any anomalies on the provision of services upon which to intervene in order to improve its performance (both economic and environmental).

Therefore GE.R.A. is a tool able to get the following results:

- activity planning and definition of the forecasting elements (service duration, number of means and human resources used, distance to be travelled, expected gasoline consumption, expected material, etc.);
- management of the maintenance activities' schedule for both means and equipment;
- punctual accounting and fissurization of the data of every service;
- direct and indirect costs allocation for every service;

- effective costs identification regarding every single service.

2.3. User Stories – Green Procurement Tool

Emilio manages a wide range of public procurements during the year. He is aware that by setting the correct parameters in the tender specification of the municipality, he could help both in achieving the goals set, and in fostering environmental friendly companies or products.

Just today, the municipality needs to make a new tender to renew the trucks for the collection of waste. Emilio wanted to include environmental criteria into the tender, as he knows that against price wise choices, more environmentally friendly options would not be able to compete. He has two main problems:

- What criteria should he include in the tender?
- How should he score them?

To this end, he opens the Green Procurement Tool and registers a new tender of type Open Tender. Then, in the next screen he chooses the aspects he wants to include in the tender specification among the ones already covered in the tool. The tool provides him with:

- the text that he should add to the tender specification including
- the information that he must retrieve from the companies
- the qualification that he must follows

Emilio now copies and pastes the text to his new tender and has two options. He can follow the standard procedures in place of his municipality or he can use the tool to manage the tender.

Emilio decides that he will use the Green Procurement Tool to manage the tender, so he will ask the applying companies to complete the information he needs to evaluate in a secure web page. Every company that wants to apply will have to register the forms shown in Figure 31.

When the tender deadline arrives, the tool will automatically compare all the proposal and will send to Emilio the report shown in Figure 32.

This report has the scores of every aspect and the final score according to the options selected by Emilio. It seems that the most economical option would be to acquire a Diesel Truck, but considering all the cost through its lifetime, it would be better to acquire a GLP powered truck. Moreover, Emilio has awarded extra points to these trucks if they can be fuelled by the biogas produced in a new treatment plant they are planning to build in the municipality. Now Emilio selects the winner, as shown in Figure 33, and continues with the normal procedures set by the municipality for awarded entities.

2.4. User Stories – Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event Planner

Emilio now needs to plan the Aste Nagusia, the biggest event in Bilbao. He knows that these events produce a lot of waste that it is not correctly managed. He wants to improve the situation, so he use the Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event Planner to plan the next issue of the event.

First, Emilio will be prompted to complete a form to score the sustainability of the event. As he will navigates through the form, the planner will give Emilio tips to improve the sustainability of the event. At the end, Emilio will need to register how he plans to monitor the quantities, such as:

- the waste generated in every sorting category
- number of clean points available for the general public and the staff
- the amount of energy used

- the amount of water spent
- the amount of emissions related to the use of transports for each waste stream
- number of reuse points
- etc.
- The tool then will automatically generate a dashboard to ease the tracking of the amount and type of waste generated in the event.

2.5 User Stories – Invoicing Module

Political consensus has been achieved and the municipality is going to change the waste tariff to a PAYT system. The mayor has put Emilio in charge of defining the low-level details of the new bill. First, Emilio needs to define the number of target groups in which the tariff will be divided and the specific characteristics of each target group.

He has set-up two target groups: industry and residential. Emilio has defined that a contract would be of type industry if it is linked to a VAT number, and of type residential if it is linked to an official identification number.

Now, Emilio has to define a tariff for every target group. First, he will choose among the variables that he can measure in the municipal database to consider which values should be considered for the fixed and the variable parts. The following table shows what he has selected in this case:

	Fixed	Variable
Industrial	Surface	Number of pickups
Residential	Cadastral value	Number of bags

Now Emilio has to decide the formula that relates these components of the tariffs. To this end, the Invoicing Module provides either a set of predefined formulas, or a visual programming tool that can help write this formula from scratch. In this case, Emilio has decided to just use one of the predefined formulas for every target group:

- *Industrial Tariff := (Surface/10+20 Number of pickups) €*
- *Residential Tariff := (Cadastral value/10 000+2 Number of bags) €*

Finally, the Invoicing tool makes a simulation using the latest data and shows Emilio a report with the most critical information:

- Recovery rate.
- Contribution of the fixed and variable part to the tax collection.
- Statistical information about the final tariff distribution for the different target groups.

3. Mid-term Planning G.E.R.A

G.E.R.A is the Italian acronym for “Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività”, which means “Resources and Activities Management”. Softline has implemented it during this project. GE.R.A is based on an optimization algorithm which gives search keys and task management processing through cost minimization and optimization in the use of staff. In fact, it can determine the human resources, vehicles and activities necessary to do a specific activity and considering, as inputs, all economic / administrative data relating to people and vehicles.

Activities can be programmed by analysing costs at each stage, from the estimate budget to real final budget, planning services through accurate matching between human and vehicle resources. Innovation, therefore, consists on the development of new parameters which the system considers to better make the activity planning. Another important task is that the system allows to manage the work plan on mobile devices, such as smartphones and / or tablets, to be used by the operators during their works on site allowing them to efficiently report the worked hours and fuel consumption. Finally, the system is integrated with call handling services enabling communication between users and the service provider in real time.

Figure 2. Components of G.E.R.A

The following sections describe in detail the components shown in Figure 2.

3.1. Databases

Data Model which describes the requested information of the system is detailed. Figure 3 represents the tables with information about operators. All the data about operators are recorded in the database to operate the optimization, monitoring and financial reports of the services. More in detail, the following aspects are recorded:

- Financial reports
- Issues
- Deadlines
- Driving licenses

- Tasks: it indicates at which activities the operator can work; a weight is given to each activity in order to point out which activity the operator should preferably do.
- Clocking in/out
- Agreements costs
- Agreements

Figure 3. Scheme of the tables which describe information about operators

Figure 4 shows the main tables describing information about vehicles and equipment.

The information regards:

- Maintenances
- Deadlines

- Costs
- Routes/RFID readings

Figure 4. Tables of information about vehicles and equipment's

Figure 5 shows the scheme of the main table containing information about Orders. A group of services composes an order. The service represents the set of activities to be done in an area of the Municipality.

The table of service has the following details:

- Frequency of the specific activity
- The zone in which the service is planned for
- The type of waste (EWC)
 - The category of the service:

1. door to door collection of a specific waste type (paper, glass, organic waste, undifferentiated waste, etc)
2. bin collection of a specific waste type (paper, glass, organic waste, undifferentiated waste, etc)
3. Household waste centre.

Activities are related to the service. An activity is represented by providing the operator's task requested, the possible category of the means provided, any equipment needed to the activity and the time slot in which the activity must be carried out.

Figure 5. Tables of data which define the Order structure

Figure 6 shows a table diagram that describes the information about the service and activity time-table. The time-table is the result of the assignment of vehicles, equipment and people to the services previously defined

Figure 6. Table diagram that describes the information about services and activities time-table.

3.2 Optimization module

The daily/weekly activity planning for make a waste collection is the output of the optimization process. The optimized collection will consist on a set of recommendations about:

- type of collection (door to door for each type of waste, bin collection, ecologic island)
- zones (this information gives to the system the frequency for the waste collection type and the modality to be used for that zone)
- resources (how many and which operators, how many and which vehicles or equipment, how many and which equipment for that kind of service at a specific frequency)

This output can be compared to the real management of the waste collection for better matches the next planning: real fuel consumption, different human resource chosen by the responsible of the waste collection because the availabilities of those planned in the software were changed, etc. Finally, the software restores all these real data to create a history of the management choices and better give the next planning.

The optimization modules will be developed by the staff of the Softline itself.

3.2.1 Optimization of service planning

The module is designed to optimize:

- ✓ personnel,
- ✓ collection vehicles
- ✓ necessary equipment for every service

to each activity with the aim of reducing company impact by optimizing personnel involvement and vehicles/equipment.

Employees are assigned for different activities by checking constraints such as:

- 1) The presence during the service period evaluating also the assigned weight which every operator has for a specify mansion.
- 2) Presence, no absence due to illness reported, holidays or other
- 3) Congruity (and validity) of the license with any necessary vehicle
- 4) check of the deadlines of the vehicle itself, etc.

The vehicles for the waste collection and the necessary equipment are used on the basis of availability in the planned period of activity.

3.2.2 Optimization of services based on the history accountability

The module analyses post-service data and tries to pinpoint margins of qualitative and quantitative improvements from a resource utilization point view.

The analysis considers:

- ✓ collected kilograms of waste per shift
- ✓ number of collections
- ✓ number of vehicle stops for collection
- ✓ km travelled
- ✓ time spent
- ✓ fuel consumption
- ✓ vehicle depreciation
- ✓ personnel costs
- ✓ consumption costs

- ✓ capacity of the trucks/vehicles
- ✓ filling of vehicle at the end of the service

Based on the data collected, various indicators are calculated to measure the cost of the service, for example:

- cost/hour
- cost/km
- percentage of vehicle use based on its operative availability,
- percentage of personnel use based on its operative availability
- volume collected / available medium volume
- etc.

Analyzing the various parameters and comparing them over a period of reference, the following parameters will be identified:

- the elements that can lead to reviewing their service planning,
- the frequency of collection and
- the use of means more coherent with the quantities to be collected

3.3 User interface

Figure 7 shows the G.E.R.A. command panel for the user-interface. It is possible to read from the left to the right the following commands/tools:

- 1) **Homepage**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the main data required by the management – Agenda, Financial report, Deadlines, Messages;
- 2.1) **Operators data**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the Operator panel (Figure 9);
- 2.2) **Attendance management**: the tool will provide where the operators can manage their incoming and exit
- 3.1) **Vehicles/equipments**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the vehicles/equipment panel (Figure 10).
- 3.2) Near the **Vehicle/Equipment** key, from up to down the first key provide the **maintenance management tool**, the second the **refueling** and the third the **analysis of vehicle costs**;
- 4.1) **Services/Order**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the Order panel (Figure 11);
- 4.2) **Time-Tables**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the time-tables panel (Figure 12);
- 5.1) **Providers**: it is possible to see a list of providers of the Company when the user selects it;
- 5.2) **Basic Tables**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the main table of the G.E.R.A. system.

Figure 7. G.E.R.A command panel

As it is shown, the system considers the whole managements of a waste collection company. As this deliverable and in particular our task regards the mid-term planning, the main section will be described in the following text.

The access to the program requires an authentication, and each user may be granted different access to data or modification (Figure 8). Only enabled users can fill in the different sections. In FACT, on the left of the panel control,

it is possible to find the type of policy that can be defined (bold text), while in the right window there are the list of components on which it is possible to apply the selected policy.

Along the bar above the mentioned windows there are six keys:

- The first two left keys indicate the “+” and “x”: they are useful to directly add and remove policies.
- The third key is the “locket” and indicate o set policy unable/able
- Then there is the “magnifying glass” key, which is used to set how policy should be shown or not.
- The “agenda” key is used to set how policy type should be only read
- The last key is used to set policy type as a custom action.

Figure 8. Policy definition for the access of the users

Specifically, the main masks that the operators will use are that for the Operator, the Equipment, the Order and the Timetable.

Each mask is composed mainly of three Sections, the name of the sections is generally the same for all masks:

- Section A is on the left of the window and represents a tree view of the folders that the user must select to open the grids at the right of the window to fill in the requested data.
- On the right of the window there are two grids indicate as Section B and C. Section B is above section C and contains the list of all Operators, Equipment, Order and Timetable (as the name of the masks indicate). When the user selects a folder from the tree view in Section A it is possible to see the detail to be filled in on the grid called Section C.
- Only the mask of the Timetable is represented with different grids because this mask is used principally to visualize the resource planning, which is the output of the whole system.

An explanation of the main mask visualized as graphic interface follow without specifically indicate each key involved on:

1) **Operators Graphic User Interface** (GUI) (Figure 9).

✓ At the left of the window, there is a tree view (**section A** in Figure 9; Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.): the main folders are three (a, b, c folders) and each one contains a list of details concerning the single operator. The c folder is not visible in this screenshot of the GUI. For better explain the Italian text of the GUI, a short list of the tree view follow:

a) **Folder a “Operators”:**

a.1) **Attendance:**

- Attendance
- Clocking in/out
- Availability
- Absences
- Trips

a.2) **Agreement:**

- Tasks
- Contracts
- Rebuke
- Fines
- Personal equipment

a.3) **Personal data**

- contact numbers
- Bank account
- **Etc.**

a.4) **Deadlines**

a.5) **Orders/Shift:** this folder is important as it connects the personal with the orders and activities

- Orders
- Services
- Shifts
- Financial Report

b) **Folder b “Tables”:**

- b.1) concessions
- b.2) Protected categories
- b.3) Licenses
- b.4) Training courses
- b.5) Tasks
- b.6) etc

c) **Folder c “tables/equipment”:**

- c.1) type of equipment
- c.2) etc

At the right of the window, there are two grids (sections B and C in Figure 9):

✓ The top one, **section B operators**, contains the details for each operator.

- ✓ The bottom one, **section C**, indicates the **tasks** in this case because the homonym folder is being selected from the section A - tree view. It is a grid to be filled in and where the main inputs required for the optimization are:
 - the B.1) **coefficient of difficulty** that indicate how much a specific task is laborious, in fact the optimization system tries to not overload an operator which tasks have a heavy weight compared to other tasks.
 - the B.2) **weight** relative to the operator: if for the same task there are more operators, the system selects those that have more weight for that job.

Figure 9. "Operator" GUI

2) Figure 10 shows the **vehicles/equipment interface**.

- ✓ At the left of the window, there is a tree view (**section A of the** *¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.*): the main folders are three (a, b, c folders).

a) **Folder a "vehicles and trucks"** contains a detailed list to be filled in about the vehicles, such as:

- deadlines
- vehicles stoppage
- depreciation
- costs
- maintenance
- fuel cards
- surveys km
- etc...

a.1) **Orders/Shift:** this folder is important as it connects the vehicles with the orders and activitier

- Orders
- Activities

- Shift
- b) **Folder b “Equipment”** contains folders to be filled in on the machines, tools and materials of the site.
- c) **Folder c “Tables”**:
- Permissions
 - Fuels
 - Vehicle categories
 - Etc
- ✓ **Section B** is a grid with the detail of the Equipment.
- ✓ **Section C** is a grid that represents the selected choice that the user has done from the Section A, the tree view. Here it is the Section C.1 where it is important to indicate the amount of consumed fuel for each vehicle.

Figure 10. “Vehicles/equipments” GUI

- 3) Figure 11 shows the **order/services GUI**.
- ✓ There is a tree view at the left of the window (**section A of Figure 11**): the main folders are two (a, b folders).
- a) **Folder a “Sectors”**:
- Categories of Services
 - Services codes
- b) **Folder a “Orders”**:
- Services
 - operator transfers
 - clients
 - operators
 - vehicles
 - equipment
 - construction sites
- ✓ **Section B** is a grid with the detail of the Orders.

- ✓ **Section C** should be fill in indicating the Sector of the Company, the service category and the Service Code
- ✓ **Section D** should be fill in indicating the specific activities of the service. In this grid is important to fill in the **Difficulty coefficient (D.1)** that will be use from the optimizer.

Figure 11. "Order" GUI

4) Figure 12 shows the **time-table GUI**.

This mask is quite different from the above described. In fact, here it is possible to visualize different grids and there is not a tree view. Briefly the main section is here reported:

- ✓ Section A is a table in which the rows are the days of the calendar, the columns are the services, the cells are marked by the operators and the vehicles assigned to the activities related to the service.
- ✓ Section B shows all the operators, vehicles and equipment available in the day. You can change the composition of a service moving by a drag and drop the resources from one table to another.
- ✓ Section D shows the calendar
- ✓ Section E is used to filter the Municipalities or Zones of a specific Order that the user wants to visualize
- ✓ Section F is used to filter the services of the Municipality or Zone of a specific Order that the user is above selected.

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Stampa Aggiorna Sistema Chiudi

Tabellone Servizi Tabellone Operatori Tabellone Automezzi Elenco Turnazioni Debug

Aggiorna Stampa SQL

A

Servizi	27/11/2017			28/11/2017			29/11/2017		
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE EST	Orario 12.00-18.00	Nominativo VITA CATALDO	Targa EM112PE	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE NORD	Orario 12.00-18.00	Nominativo VITA CATALDO	Targa EM112PE	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE OVEST	Orario 12.00-18.00	Nominativo VITA CATALDO	Targa EM112PE	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa
PAP ORGANICO	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa

B

Operatori	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco Piccione Santo	VITA CATALDO Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco	VITA CATALDO Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco	VITA CATALDO Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco

Automezzi	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR

Attrezzature	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
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D

novembre 2017

Filtro Comuni/Zone

- Comesse
- URB - SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI
- BON - ENEL PUGLIA E BASILICATA
- MICRORACCOLTA
- MAC - VESTAS

E

Filtro Servizi

- Servizi
- ALTRE OPERE
- BONIFICA AMIANTO E/R
- BONIFICA SITI CONTAMINATI
- DEMOLIZIONI CIVILI / ID
- IMPIANTI TECNOLOGICI
- INDAGINI E ANALISI AM
- OPERE EDILI
- RACCOLTA RSU E ASSIEME
- RACCOLTA RIFIUTI SPE
- TRASPORTI DA CENTRI
- TRASPORTI DA IMPIANTI

F

GeRA - Comesse Calendario Turni GeRA - Automezzi/Attrezzature GeRA - Operatori

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Figure 12. Time-Tables GUI

4. Long-Term Planning

One of the main challenges of simulating human societies is taking into consideration all the complex decisions and events that influence everyday decisions. All individuals want to achieve a set of goals for which it is necessary to interact, compete and cooperate with others. It is this complex behaviour that needs to be tackled from a different point of modelling taking into play physical, social, cultural and economic aspects of everyday relations.

GeoSmartSim (GSS) is a Geographical Simulations Engine [1] combining Geographic Information System's techniques with a Multi-Agent System [2] to reproduce dynamic urban environments. Multi-agent environments allow a bottom-up modelling, where all agents collaborate and compete against each other while interacting with the environment. In this way, a model is defined and run through a simulation, whose results vary depending on both the characteristics of the agents and their decision processes. The advantage of this approach is the feasibility to parameterize different scenarios and evaluate how the different individuals behaviour and interactions are affected each time.

The platform will receive a scenario built with the Scenario Definition Tool containing information about the features and entities that need to take place in the simulation. Please note that a scenario will contain both data from the Current State and Other Information (that could be historical, future plans or from a what-if scenario). It will then process the scenario by running all the agents in a Monte-Carlo simulation and finally bulk the results into the Context Broker hosting simulations database. Figure 13 graphically describes this flow of information.

Figure 13. Components of the Long-Term Planning tool.

4.1. Scenario Definition tool

The Scenario Definition tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core. Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1 (Figure 14).

When the user accesses the Scenario Definition tool, they will be presented with a **list of the simulations that are currently active** (Figure 15). At first glance, the user will be able to identify the important details about the simulations, such as the name, a short description of its purpose, a map stating its geographical boundaries, and its status (running, finished, error, etc). The user can either **create** a new scenario or click on any of the existing simulations to **launch a detailed view of the specific configuration**.

Figure 14. Access to Scenario Definition Tool through the side menu of W4T-Core

Figure 15. Main view of the Scenario Definition Tool

4.1.1. Creation of a new simulation scenario

When the user selects the option to **Create a new simulation**, they will be presented with a guide that will help them configure the new simulation scenario (Figure 16) through the definition of the following inputs.

- **Basic details.** Define attributes such as the name, the description, and the geographical (location) and temporal (start and end date) boundaries of the simulation.
- **Simulation Model:** Choose from a list of available optimization models, the one that will be tested on the simulation. Each model will be parametrized according to its specific operation through a JSON configuration file that can be uploaded by the user.
- **Data source:** All simulation scenarios need data on which to perform the simulation. For example, this data may include the definition of the amount and type of people in a certain geographical zone, the location of the waste containers, the routes of the waste trucks, etc. The user can either select to use t a) real data retrieved from the current status and measurements of the pilots, b) simulated data from a previously configured scenario, or c) create new scenario with new set of data (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Create new simulation scenario within the Scenario Definition Tool

Figure 17. Create new scenario resources

4.1.2. Editing an existing simulation scenario

When the user selects *an existing simulation scenario*, they will be presented with a view, similar to the one used during its creation. In this case, all the configuration data will be already loaded. From this view the user can select to either stop the simulation and rerun it with newly configured parameters, or cancel the simulation.

Figure 18. Edit View of the Long-Term Planning Tool

The scenarios will follow the schema described in Deliverable D2.1, which defines the types of entities to be used and monitored in the Waste4Think modules. The entities to use in what-if scenarios are:

- **Citizens:** People, shops or industries hosted in a certain municipality or geographic area will be modelled as *WasteEntities* from the schema defined in Deliverable D2.1, Section 4.2.3. It will be possible to, on the one hand, load the real-world data from the Context Broker to recreate a real-world scenario or, on the other hand, manually or through a shapefile format file to create fictional citizens, shops or industries for what-if scenario testing:
 - *WasteEntity*: Each instance where waste is created, transformed or consumed, belonging to a *WasteEntityType* and containing the location of the entity together with the specific features that describe the recycling behaviour, awareness and generation pattern.
 - *WasteEntityType*: Description of a group of citizens, shops, industries etc. that will take part in the waste flow, generating, transforming or consuming waste. For each entity type, the usual waste inputs and outputs will be enumerated.
- **Recycling behaviours:** Model for characterizing the way each citizen generates and throws its waste. One of the main points for the simulations is emulating in a reliable way, the behaviour citizens have when generating wastes and choosing how and where to throw them. The recycling behaviour model will take into consideration all socio-economic aspects of each citizen together with its recycling awareness and create the actions each individual will perform. These statistical models are usually built using Regression models or Generalized linear models that are trained from raw data [3]. Our model will combine state of the art models, raw data and surveys carried out to the project pilots.

- **Deposit points:** Traditional containers or newly introduced door2door systems are modelled through the DepositPoint entities. These are composed of the model defined in Deliverable D2.1, Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2. Just the same as with citizens, DepositPoint data will be extracted both from the Context Broker for real world scenarios or from manual and SHP files for what-if fiction scenarios. The entities to load are as follows:
 - *Waste*: The material discarded by citizens or business' after primary use. A waste can be almost any material which is worthless for the user. Nevertheless, it can be useful for another agent as input.
 - *WasteCategory*: A higher level category that describes some features all of its child wastes share such as origin, material, fabrication process, etc.
 - *SortingType*: Grouping of wastes that are collected together in a country or service area. Sorting types usually vary according to legislation, collecting company or technical requirements. Traditional sorting types are usually light packaging, glass bottles, paper and cardboard, organic waste and refuse.
 - *DepositPoint*: Place where waste is deposited for its collection. It covers from traditional containers to less usual methods such as a personal plastic bag (in door2door systems), pneumatic waste dumpsters, fixed collection centers, mobile collection centers, etc.
 - *DepositPointType*: Container, bag, dumpster, etc. models with their features that are common to all DepositPoints from this type such as waste it contains, capacity, color, height, width, price, etc.
 - *DepositPointIsle*: A group of DepositPoints that belong together in a geographic area. This can be useful for calculations at DepositPointIsle level where there are more than one DepositPoint in a place and users tend to use them indifferently resulting in irregular measurements.
- **Waste Collection Systems:** Waste collection systems will be built using the model from Deliverable D2.1, Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.4. Scenario data will be gathered from the real-world scenario hosted in the Context Broker or from manually and SHP files created data. The six main entities involved in waste management systems are:
 - *Waste*: The material discarded by citizens or business' after primary use. A waste can be almost any material which is worthless for the user. Nevertheless, it can be useful for another agent as input.
 - *WasteCategory*: A higher level category that describes some features all of its child wastes share such as origin, material, fabrication process, etc.
 - *SortingType*: Grouping of wastes that are collected together in a country or service area. Sorting types usually vary according to legislation, collecting company or technical requirements. Traditional sorting types are usually light packaging, glass bottles, paper and cardboard, organic waste and refuse.
 - *CollectionRoute*: A particular transport route with all properties which are common to multiple itinerary instances belonging to such model. A route is a way to identify a journey that is regularly made by a given transport in an agency.
 - *Itinerary*: A scheduled itinerary for a certain date and vehicle. It contains a list of ordered *ItinerarySegments* the vehicle should follow together with the estimated arrival and departure time.
 - *ItinerarySegment*: ItinerarySegment contains the information of the pieces that build the entire itinerary with the departure and arrival entities and times.

- **Transport Networks:** Road, highways, footways and paths will be loaded from the volunteer geographic information OpenStreetMap [CITA]. OpenStreetMap is a free, editable map of the whole world that is being built by volunteers containing a full detailed roadmap which is constantly updated by volunteers. Map elements use a key-value definition schema for describing each feature and its attributes. The key `highway=*` is the main key used for identifying any kind of road, street or path. The value of the key helps indicate the importance of the highway within the road network as a whole [5].

OpenStreetMap's data schema will automatically be downloaded and used for transport network modelling inside GSS. For every simulation, all the roads, highways and footways will be downloaded and connected in a transport network graph that is going to be used.

4.2. GeoSmartSim Simulation Engine

All GSS simulations are structured in three main pillars: agents, environment and skills. The next sections explain in detail every one of the pillars:

4.2.1. Agents

All the entities interfering in a scenario are modelled as agents. Each of these, is a piece of semi-autonomous software acting to carry out a task that satisfy its needs. This therefore, allows a finer parametrization of each individual in a more truthful way.

All agents have some basic properties and methods that identify them both geographically and logically:

- **Id:** Identification of the agent.
- **Type:** Class type of the agent.
- **Geometry:** Geographical representation and location of the agent.
- **Skills:** A set of skills for the agent to be able to perform operations.
- **Behaviour:** An active loop that will be executed constantly for the agent to select which operation to perform next and reach its goal.
- **Meta properties:** Extendable property system to add additional properties.

According to the complexity of these attributes agents are categorised in two different groups whether they have their own active behaviour, or they just react to stimuli:

4.2.1.1. Intelligent agents

Autonomous Agents constitute the traditional agents in a Multi-Agent System (MAS). They are scheduled to follow a certain behaviour and are active elements that start the actions. Their execution loop will be implemented with all the active process they follow to achieve their goals.

- **Citizens:** active agents in the simulations, citizens will be located and parametrized in the environment according to the data provided from the scenario editor tool. Each citizen will have a set of preferences that will characterize their recycling awareness, amount of waste they generate and maximum walking distance they are willing to travel to the container. Everyday agents will generate waste according to generation patterns stored and will try to throw it at the nearest container they have. Depending on the available deposit points, collection days and recycling awareness, citizens will make good or bad use of them.
- **Vehicle Drivers:** active agents that drive the collection vehicles. Vehicle drivers will have the *Skill* to schedule the itinerary for their assigned deposit points and reproduce the itinerary emptying or collecting the points and filling the vehicle. Altering the schedules will change the environmental, social and economic impacts together with how the citizens will use the deposit points.

4.2.1.2. Passive agents

Passive agents are those entities who, although having some logic inside, just react to the actions of other Entities. Namely, they provide or receive information from agents and other passive entities. Their behaviour loop must be empty and other agents will access and alter this agent's properties.

- **Transport Network:** roads, highways, footways and paths for the study area that will compound the environment in which the agents will live. Transport network will be downloaded from the volunteer geographic information OpenStreetMap creating a routing graph with the roads and highways for vehicles and footways and steps citizens can use for travelling.
- **Deposit Points:** representing traditional containers or Door2Door deposit points hosting one single sorting type. Each deposit point has its own capacity, filling level and location. These passive agents will just react to the citizens waste throwing by increasing their filling level and to the vehicles by emptying their filling levels.
- **Waste Treatment plants:** places where a certain waste is recycled. These agents will transform the received waste into resources (secondary RAW materials or energy) or just stored them (landfills).
- **Vehicles:** combustion or electric vehicles in charge of performing the collection itinerary. This passive agent will follow the orders of the driver and will emit emissions to the atmosphere together with fuel (if motorized) or energy (if electric) consumption.

4.2.2. Agent Environment

Agent Environments provide the virtual world where agents inhabit and the information and rules for them to act. Within MAS technologies, the Agent Environment concept has been recognised as an independent and living element which is essential to model dynamic real-world problems. Real Environments are inherently dynamic, that is, change beyond the agent's control and therefore this dynamism must be modelled explicitly as part of the simulated Environment by implementing processes that can change its own state.

- **Physical environment:** This layer of the environment is the one that models the geographical aspects of the entities that coexist in it. Deploys a Geographic Information System managing and limiting the movements agents can perform in the environment.
- **Time environment:** Section for time managing in the virtual world of the agents. They will be synchronized and scheduled according to the time the environment they live in.
- **Climate environment:** Atmospheric layers regarding temperature, humidity, sun irradiation and other measures that represent the weather situation of the environment.
- **Social Environment:** GeoSmartSim enables a SIGNAL/SLOT mechanism agent to use to receive interactions from other entities. Agents can subscribe slots to signals that other entities emit, resulting their slot being invoked when the emitter sends some information.
- **Network Environment:** For network modelling purposes (transport, water, power, etc.), two special classes GSSGraphEdge and GSSGraphNode are provided for agents to inherit from them. All agents that implement any of these two classes will be elements of a graph contained in the Network Environment.
- **Execution environment:** The environment oversees managing each agent turn to behave. The execution environment ensures all agents receive their execution time according to their needs and action times.

4.2.3. Skills

Skills are the degree of competence a living entity has when carrying out a certain task. GeoSmartSim implements a large battery of skills that enable agents sensing the environment, memorizing, processing information, making decisions, etc. Both intelligent and passive agents can have a set of skills to interact with the environment and alter its properties:

- Intelligent Agent Skills:
 - *Generate waste skill:* Waste generation behaviour for each citizen, shop or industry.
 - *Search Deposit points skills:* Environment look up skill for finding a citizen's best deposit points.

- *Decide use of deposit points skill*: Each agent's thinking process of whether to correctly use the deposit points or not according to distances, volume of waste and awareness.
- **Passive Agent Skills**
 - *Contain waste skill*: Skill of accepting waste from active agents until it reaches its maximum capacity.
 - *Vehicle move skill*: Ability for a combustion or electric vehicle to move. The vehicle will consume some resources for this purpose and emit several impacts and gases to the atmosphere.
 - *Transform waste skill*: Process of transforming waste into others for treatment plants.

4.3. Optimization Module

This module will oversee the different optimizations that the Long-Term Planner module could perform. The next sections will introduce the main aspects of both the GeoSimulation and the algorithms used to complete the task.

4.3.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

The KPIs that come into play in the simulations are extracted from the global KPI list of the project described in Deliverable D1.3. Table 2 contains the list and objectives of the KPIs for the Planning Module. These KPIs will be used for scenario improvement evaluation in each of the modules described below.

Table 2. List of KPIs selected for the optimization.

Objectives	KPIs
Reduction of the municipal waste generation	T1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation (kg/year)
To eliminate the primary waste deposited into landfills and to maximize waste reuse and recycling	T2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted
	T3 Decrease of the average of waste sent to final disposal
	T3.1 Dry recyclables to primary destination (%)
	T3.2 Organic recyclables to primary destination (%)
To improve the integral waste management service	T.3.3 Residual waste to primary destination (%)
	E.1.1 net GHG emissions (kg CO2/ kg of waste) collection & treatment
	C.1.2 Treatment canon (€/ton)
	C.1.3.1 Collection and Transport cost (€)
	C1.3.2 Final management cost (€)
	C1.3.3 Other common costs (€)
	C1.1 Budget applied to awareness and prevention campaigns (€)
S.2.1 Number of workers (n)	

4.3.2. Waste generation patterns optimization

This module will reproduce and simulate the citizens waste generation and how different social actions and incentives influence in their recycling awareness. To this end, this module will simulate the effect that different social actions will have on the citizens waste generation and recycling behaviour.

The main agents involved in the simulation will be:

- **Citizens:** the scenario will need the location of citizens together with their waste throwing characterization, recycling awareness and the maximum distance that a citizen is willing to walk to throw the waste separately.
- **Social Actions and Incentives:** List of strategies to be applied in the municipality to evaluate their effects in the citizens.

The goal is to be able to prioritize (or know) which social actions and incentives may have the most beneficial effects on the municipality and their side effects with respect to the KPIs defined in Table 2. The module will use evolutionary algorithms (EA) for evaluating if new scenarios provide a lower or greater waste generation and recycling rate. Each iteration, the EA will modify a population of scenarios changing the awareness and incentives of the citizens.

4.3.3. Waste sorting method and deposit points location module

This module will be in charge of assess the best sorting method for the scenario along with the optimization of the deposit points. First, the user should select the number of different fractions to collect. Then, the module will optimize the localization of the deposit points. Please note that pneumatic collection system could be assimilated to this one just changing the impact of the construction and operation of the infrastructure.

As it is known that recycling rates decrease with respect to the distance to the collection points, this module will evaluate the current situation of them to suggest a better location in order to improve recycling rates while keeping controlled the rest of impacts. To this end, the user will need to set some input scenario from which the agents and skills will be modelled as follows:

- **Citizens:** the scenario will need the location of citizens together with their waste throwing characterization, recycling awareness and the maximum distance that a particular citizen is willing to walk to throw the waste separately.
- **Deposit Points:** Models, collecting sorting types and initial location for deposit points. This will be used as baseline scenario from which to compare if simulated solutions improve the current scenario.
- **Transport Network:** for the citizens to find their nearest containers and make use of them will be loaded automatically to cover the study area.

The module will also use EA for evaluating if new scenarios provide a lower or greater recycling rate. Each iteration, the EA will modify a population of scenarios changing the location and properties of the deposit points. After each modification the algorithm will perform a simulation of the behaviour of the citizen in the new scenario and evaluate the result with respect of several of the KPIs defined in Deliverable D1.3. It will then start a new iteration using the population of improved scenarios as the base to be modified. Changing the location, sizes and collection days of the containers will then affect the decisions of the citizens and result in a better or worse separation rate. Finally, the EA will always keep the best scenario.

It is important to note that a door to door (D2D) collection system should not need this type of optimization as every portal should have its own collection point.

4.3.4. Route Scheduling Optimization Module

This module will evaluate the impact of the current routes used to collect the waste and look for improvements in both the routes and vehicle schedules with respect to the criteria detailed in Table 2.

To this end, the user will need to set some input scenario from which the agents and skills will be modelled as follows:

- **Deposit Points:** Models and initial location for deposit points. The deposit points will be immovables and will be used for scheduling their collection in as many routes as needed.
- **Vehicles:** Model and main features of the vehicles available for collecting the points. The module will try to balance collection among several vehicles if needed.
- **Vehicle Drivers:** Drivers will control the vehicles travelling through the scenario using them. This will provoke the vehicles to emit gases and consume fuel for impacts calculation of the proposed schedule.
- **Transport Network:** for the citizens to find their nearest containers and make use of them will be loaded automatically to cover the study area.

The module will also use a EA strategy for making changes in a set (population) of route schedules (including the current one) and evaluate if the result provides a lower or greater impact. Each iteration the algorithm will modify the periodicity, route itineraries, driver assigned deposit points, number of vehicles or vehicles types of the element in the population of solutions. Just the same as for Section 3.3.1, the resulting scenario will be compared keeping the best scenario with respect to the previous KPIs and passing it to a new iteration.

4.3.5. Best selection of treatments

This module will select the best collection of treatments plants (including the storage of biogas) for the scenario. Aspects like the technologies, the sizing and localization of different treatments plant will be considered. The algorithm will simulate the transport of the different fractions of waste generated in the scenario to the different treatments plants and will evaluate the impact of every solution with respect to the KPIs in Table []. Every treatment plant modelled will have the following characteristics:

- **Economic costs:** including building and demolition costs, operational costs
- **RAW materials:** efficiency in recovery of secondary RAW materials
- **Environmental impacts:** the same aspects as in Section 3.3.2.
- **Social response** that of the construction or management of the treatment plant will have over the citizens.
- **Legal restrictions** with respect to distance to the population and surface requirements to be able to operate.

As before, a EA will be used to perform the optimization. In this case, the EA will first create a set of solutions that consists of:

- a selection of treatments between the pool of potential treatments between: landfill, incineration, mechanically-biological classification plant, classification plant, anaerobic digestion, composting, recycling plant for the different fractions (including nappies, R20), and valorisation of the different fractions (including R19 and R20)
- a potential localization (between a set of potential localization fixed in the scenario) and finally,
- a sizing for every treatment plan.

As before, the EA then modify this population of solutions and will run a simulation to evaluate it with respect to the previous KPIs defined. As in Section 3.3.1, the resulting scenario will be compared keeping the best scenario with respect to the previous KPIs and passing it to a new iteration.

4.3.6. Overall optimization module

All the above-mentioned modules will allow both their use independently or their combined use in a co-evolutionary algorithm. Each module's EA is executed separately sending its resultant scenario as input for the next module to optimize. Therefore, it will be possible to create multi objectives optimization scenarios (in the sense of the objects to optimize, not the objectives).

5. Green Procurement

The objective of the Green Procurement tool, further detailed in Deliverable D1.3, is to provide the user with the mechanisms to build and evaluate a public tender based on green principles. The following sections present several mock-ups of the user interface explaining the main actions that the users can perform.

5.1. Access to the Green Procurement tool

The Green Procurement tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 19. Access to the Green Procurement Tool.) Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1.

Figure 19. Access to the Green Procurement Tool.

On access, the user will be presented with the two main functionalities of the module:

- a) **Create new green procurement tender.** This functionality provides a wizard, a kind of helper, that lets the user create a new tender and define the parameters that are going to be evaluated to comply with the green procurement principles. Details of the options to be included can be found in Deliverable D1.3.
- b) **Monitor existing green procurement tenders.** This functionality allows to edit unpublished tenders, add new offers to published tenders, and close tenders so that the submitted offers can be evaluated.

Figure 20. Functionalities of the green Procurement Module.

5.2. Create new green procurement

When the user selects the option **Create new green procurement**, the tool will provide a form to introduce the necessary data to define the general details of the document, such as the product on which the tender is based and its period of validity (Figure 20). The specific fields for the organization details of the tenderer will be automatically retrieved and filled from the user profile. Nevertheless, these fields will be editable in case the user needs to modify them.

Figure 21. Green Procurement Questionnaire.

Once the general details have been defined, the user will then proceed to choose the specific aspects that will be evaluated in the tender (economical, environmental, social, etc.) and the general scoring criterion. The information about the scoring criterion implemented can be found in Section 6.7 of Deliverable D1.3. Please note that now only one scoring criterion is implemented but the tool is prepared to allow different scoring criteria.

For each type of aspect, the user will be presented with a view on which they can select the particular aspects relevant to the tender, provide a score determining the importance of the aspect within the overall evaluation, and assign threshold values to help discriminate offers based on priorities (Figure 21, Figure 22, and Figure 23).

The screenshot shows the 'Green Procurement' web application interface. The title is 'Green Procurement' and the URL is 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The sidebar on the left has 'Details' selected. The main content area is titled 'Select economic aspects' and contains six cards, each representing a different economic aspect:

- Purchase cost (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 100,00€. Maximum: 250,00€.
- Investment costs (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 1000,00€. Maximum: 1200,00€.
- Operating costs (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 3,00€. Maximum: 4,00€.
- Maintenance costs (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 50,00€. Maximum: 60,00€.
- Taxes/other costs (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 10,00€. Maximum: 20,00€.
- End of life costs (€)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 5,00€. Maximum: 5,00€.

A 'Next' button is located at the bottom right of the configuration area.

Figure 22. Definition of the socio-economical aspects of the green procurement.

The screenshot shows the 'Green Procurement' web application interface. The title is 'Green Procurement' and the URL is 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The sidebar on the left has 'Social' selected. The main content area is titled 'Select social aspects' and contains six cards, each representing a different social aspect:

- Staff training (h/p)**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 3h. Maximum: 10h.
- Gender equality**: Req. Point 10. Required:
- Employment creation**: Req. Point 15. Minimum: 100,00 kg. Maximum: 300,00 kg.
- Innovation level**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 1000,00€. Maximum: 1200,00€.
- Conflict minerals**: Req. Point 10. Required:
- Cooperation**: Req. Point 10. Minimum: 1000,00€. Maximum: 1200,00€.

A 'Next' button is located at the bottom right of the configuration area.

Figure 23. Definition of the social aspects of the green procurement.

Figure 24. Definition of the environmental aspects of the green procurement

If the user wants to change the specification of any of the economic, environmental or social aspects they can do so by clicking on the Edit button located on the top left position (Figure 25. Edit the specification of the aspects..

Figure 25. Edit the specification of the aspects.

After the definition and parameterization of the green aspects of the tender, **all the data introduced by the user will be integrated and formatted into an editable document** that will become the final specification of the tender. The user will be able to modify the document to their liking so as to properly define and include any additional information that must be taken into consideration. The user will also be able to save the tender for later reviewing or export the document for printing. The text shown on Figure 26 is used just as an example.

Figure 26. Final revision of the tender.

5.3. Monitor existing green procurement

When the user selects the option **Monitor a green procurement**, the tool will provide a list of all the tenders created by the user (Figure 27). At first glance, the user will be able to identify the important details about the tenders, such as the date of publication, the number of offers submitted, and the status. Specifically, the status of a tender refers to the three possible states of the tender lifecycle, as follows:

- Unpublished:** The user has already begun to elaborate a new tender, but it is not yet available to the public. Some details or aspects may or may not be fully defined. The user can modify all the data and aspects of an unpublished tender. The user can not add any offers to an unpublished tender.
- Published:** The tender is already fully defined and is available to the public. Therefore, the user cannot modify any of its details or aspects. The user will be able to review the specification and upload the new offers that match the tender requirements.
- Closed:** When the period of validity of the tender comes to an end, the tender is automatically closed. A user cannot modify the details or aspects of a closed tender, nor add additional offers.

The user can access the full details of each tender by clicking on its name to consult the complete text (Figure 27. List of green procurements.), and the aspects being evaluated (Figure 29). The modification of this information will only be possible if the tender is still in unpublished status. If a tender is already closed, the user can additionally see the offer to which the tender was awarded (Figure 28), as well as all the other offers that were submitted.

A Web Page

← → ↻ https://

WASTE 4think Green Procurement

Select a tender to view

Q search

Name	Description	Start date	Status	Offers	Publish	Close
Tender1	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-01-01	Closed	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender2	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-01-02	Closed	2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender3	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-02-11	Published	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender4	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-03-27	Published	7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender5	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-04-04	Closed	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender9	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-02	Published	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender10	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-11	Closed	20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender11	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-21	Closed	15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender12	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-06-16	Unpublished	15	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender13	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-06-16	Unpublished	12	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 27. List of green procurements.

A Web Page

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WASTE 4think Green Procurement

Details

Aspects

Offers

Results

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Edit
Export
Next

Figure 28. Text of the green procurement

Figure 29. Aspects evaluated in the green procurement

A user can add offers to a published tender through the corresponding section (Figure 30). At first glance, this section provides a list of the offers that have already been submitted, detailing the name of the submitter as well as the date of submission. From this view, the user can choose to view the specific details of an offer, consult the history of offers made by a specific submitter (Figure 31), or add a new offer by filling the corresponding form with the necessary data to evaluate the aspects of the tender (Figure 32).

Figure 30. List of offers submitted to the tender.

Figure 31. History of offer submitted by a specific organization.

Figure 32. Add new offer to the green procurement

As mentioned before, when the period of validity of a tender comes to an end, the tender will be automatically closed. The user will then be able to access a new view that summarizes and ranks the offers submitted to the tender in terms of compliance with the aspects defined in its formulation. The user will be able to review the specific details of each offer, choose the filter for ranking, see those offers that do not meet the threshold values expected, and select the final offer to which the tender will be awarded (Figure 34).

Figure 33. Rank of submitted offers to a specific green procurement.

Figure 34. Selection of offer that is awarded the green procurement.

6. Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event Planner

The purpose of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner, further detailed in Deliverable D1.3, is to provide the user with a tool to identify what amount and type of waste is generated in a specific event or ecosystem, for example a monitored building, whether residential or commercial, and to delve into the reasons behind its generation and evaluate a set of correction actions such as the green procurement, prevention campaigns, or the measures resulting from the innovative teaching materials at schools or citizen science.

6.1. Access to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool

The Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Access to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool

When the user accesses the tool, they will be presented with the list of Zero-Waste dashboards they have already created. The user will be able to select any dashboard and visualize its specific details. A Zero Waste dashboard is a type of dashboard that is specially dedicated to the monitoring of both Zero-Waste Events and Zero-Waste Ecosystems. The general behaviour and functionalities of the dashboards are detailed in Deliverable D2.1.

Figure 36. Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event dashboards.

6.2. Monitor existing Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event dashboards

On access to this section, the user will be presented with the details of the Zero-Waste dashboards created by them. At first glance, the user will be able to see the monitoring start and end dates of the Zero-Waste dashboard (related to the start and end dates of the Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event), configure whether a dashboard should be visible in the main page of the Zero-Waste Planner Tool, or delete the dashboard.

Figure 37. Existing Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Events dashboards.

6.3. Create new Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event

When the user selects the creation of a new Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event, they will be presented with a helper that will guide them through each section (Description, Waste Management, Internal Services, Communication activities, Evaluation, etc.) of the Zero-Waste questionnaire so that they fill in the required fields according to the classification explained in Deliverable D1.3 (Figure 38 and Figure 39). Each of the sections will be accessible through a side menu, for example, in the form of tabs.

Figure 38. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (general description).

Figure 39. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (waste management).

After answering all the questionnaire fields of each of the sections, the user will be presented with the Evaluation view (Figure 40). The Evaluation view lets the user create an automatic dashboard of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event. The user will configure the dashboard by providing, if possible, information about the identifiers of the entities that can be monitored, such as the waste containers that will give service to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event or the KPIs. With the defined monitored entities, the Zero-Waste Planner tool will create a dashboard, on which the user can follow the state of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem or the Zero-Waste Event.

Figure 40. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (evaluation).

The final view (Figure 41) visualizes the results obtained from the evaluation of the user's answers to the questionnaire, detailing the degree of compliance of the answers to the parameters defined for the evaluation of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Events (see Deliverable D1.3).

Figure 41. Results of the evaluation of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event.

7. Social Actions

The objective of the Social Actions tool, further detailed in Deliverables D4.1, is to provide the user with the mechanisms to build and evaluate social actions. The following sections present several mock-ups of the user interface explaining the main actions that the users can perform.

7.1. Access to the Social Actions tool

The Social Actions tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 42. Access to the Social Actions tool).

Figure 42. Access to the Social Actions tool.

On access to the Social Actions tool, the user will be presented with a list of the existing social strategies defined by them. This list gives a general information about each strategy and allows to **create, edit or delete** them.

Figure 43. Main view of the Social Actions tool.

7.2. Add new Strategy

When the user selects the option to **Create New Strategy** they will be presented with a guide, which will help them introduce the specific details of the new Strategy, such as the name, the description, the area of coverage, the target groups towards whom the strategy is focused, etc. (Figure 44. Form to introduce the detail the Social Strategy).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'Green Procurement' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. The form contains the following fields: 'Name' (text input), 'Start' (date picker), 'End' (date picker), 'Description' (text area), 'Area' (text area), 'Target groups' (text input), 'Objective' (text input), 'Stages' (text input), and 'Cost' (text input). At the bottom, there are three buttons: 'Actions', 'Prev', and 'Next'.

Figure 44. Form to introduce the detail the Social Strategy.

On access to a specific Strategy, the user will be presented with a list of the related Social Actions. This list gives a general information about each action and allows to **create, edit or delete** them (Figure 45).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'W4T Rules Manager' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. The sub-header is 'Promote waste separation'. Below this, there is a 'View Mode' selector with grid, list, and table icons, a search bar, and a 'Per page' selector with options for 5, 10, and All. The main content area displays a list of social actions:

- Create New Social Action**: Represented by a plus sign icon.
- Distribute Flyers**: Represented by a flag icon. Description: 'Distribute flyers with about what and what not are adecuate waste to organic container.' Includes a red trash icon.
- Meetings on the town hall**: Represented by a flag icon. Description: 'Meet with the citizens and promote neighbourhood actions.' Includes a red trash icon.

At the bottom, there is a pagination bar with buttons for 1, 2, 3, 4, an ellipsis, and Last.

Figure 45. Social Actions of a specific Strategy.

7.3. Add new Social Action

When the user selects the option to **Add a new Social Action** they will be presented with a guide, which will help them to introduce the specific details of the new Strategy, such as the name, the description, the period of application, the target groups towards whom the action is focused, etc. (Figure 46).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'Green Procurement' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. On the left, a sidebar contains three tabs: 'Details' (selected), 'Monitoring', and 'Results'. The main content area contains the following form fields:

- Name:** A single-line text input field.
- Description:** A multi-line text area.
- Period:** Two date pickers labeled 'Start' and 'End', each with a calendar icon.
- Promoter:** A single-line text input field.
- Area served:** A multi-line text area.
- Target groups:** A single-line text input field.

A 'Next' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 46. Details of the Social Action.

Once the general details have been introduced, the user will be guided to the Monitoring view. In this view, the user will specify the KPIs that will help calculate the impact of the application of the Social Action (Figure 47).

The screenshot shows the same 'Social Actions' page, but the 'Monitoring' tab is selected in the sidebar. The form fields are:

- Objectives:** A multi-line text area.
- Stages:** A single-line text input field.
- Stakeholders amount:** A single-line text input field.
- Methodology:** A multi-line text area.

Below these fields are two sections for selecting KPIs and Targets:

- KPIs:** An 'Add' button is above a list with three items: 'Kpi_Sorting_paper_correct', 'Kpi_Sorting_paper_incorrect', and 'Kpi_Sorting_package_correct'. Each item has a 'remove' icon.
- Target:** An 'Add' button is above a list with two items: 'waste_tipe_paper' and 'waste_type_other'. Each item has a 'remove' icon.

'Prev' and 'Next' buttons are located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 47. Monitoring of the Social Action.

7.3. Add results to the Social Action

When the period of application of the social action finishes, the user will have to provide both quantitative and qualitative results to analyse the impact of the social action. To do so, the Social Actions module will provide with the necessary form to fill in the data (Figure 48). Please note that the specific forms that will gather the qualitative and quantitative results will vary per Strategy. Figure 48 provides just an example.

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "Green Procurement" with the URL "https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/". The page header includes the "WASTE 4think" logo and the title "Social Actions". On the left, a green sidebar contains three menu items: "Details", "Monitoring", and "Results". The main content area contains the following form fields:

- Stakeholder (Real)**: A text input field.
- Success**: A rating system with four filled stars and one empty star.
- Cost**: A text input field.
- Per citizen**: A text input field.
- Social Impact**: A large text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Economical Impact**: A large text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Lesson learned**: A large text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Resources URL**: A large text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Other**: A large text area with a vertical scrollbar.

At the bottom right of the form, there are two buttons: "Prev" and "Save".

Figure 48. Social Actions results.

8. Invoicing

The objective of the Invoicing Module, further detailed in Deliverables D2.1 and D5.1, is to provide an interface to create and estimate the results of new invoices models fed with data from the system. The invoice module will help in the creation of new invoices models that will be tested upon real and simulated data to test the viability and sustainability of the different models.

8.1. Access to the Invoicing tool

The Invoicing tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core. Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1 (Figure 49).

Figure 49. Access to the Invoicing Module

8.2. Manage of the invoices

On access to the Invoice Module, the user will be presented with a list of the existing invoices defined by them. This list gives a general information about each invoice and allows to **create, edit or delete** them.

Figure 50. Main view of the Invoicing Module

8.3. Creation of a new invoice model

If the user selects the option to **Create a new invoicing** model, they will be presented with a helper that will guide them in this creation process. The creation process is split into three steps, each one represented by a different view. These views will be also accessible through a side menu, for example, through tabs located on the left side:

- The **Details** view allows to manage the fixed and variable cost elements that will be covered by the invoicing model (Figure 51). The user can also select the scenario on which they want to test the new model: a) *real* with the measurements being recorded directly from the pilots, b) *simulated* with any of the simulations scenarios already defined by the user. The user will also provide a relevant name for the invoicing model for future reference.
- The **Target group** view allows to define the target groups on which the new invoicing model will be tested (citizens, business, educational organizations, etc.) (Figure 52). The user will also be able to define the rules that determine the belonging of an element to a specific group. On selection of each target group, the user is presented with the set of variables relevant to that group that can then be used to build the final formula for the invoicing model.
- The **Report** view allows to test the new invoicing model. For that, the user will be presented with a special type of dashboard that will graphically present how the specific parts of the invoice model affect each target group (Figure 53). This view will also feature a control panel that will let the user adjust the formula of the invoice model in terms of the variables that are affected within each target group and type of the cost (fixed or variable), and the specific arithmetic operations to perform.

W4T Rules Manager

https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview

Invoicing

WASTE 4think

Details

Target Group

Report

Name:

Scenario: Zamudio:Real

Fixed Cost		Total	60k
Concept	Quantity		
Infraestructure	10k		
Salaries	50k		
Add New	-		

Variable cost		Total	60k
Vairable	Origin	Cost	
Bag	Manual	60k	
Add New			

Cancel Next

Figure 51. Definition of the elements of the invoice.

W4T Rules Manager

https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview

Invoicing

WASTE 4think

Details

Target Group

Report

Definition

Name	Rule	Count	Erase
Citizen	rule_is_citizen	3.000	
Business	rule_is_business	200	
Add New	-		

Variables

Name	affect	property	erase
Area	Fixed	area	
Bags	Variable	bags_produced	
Add New	-		

Cancel Report

Figure 52. Definition of the target group.

Figure 53. Dashboard of the Invoicing Module

9. References

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Comments from external reviewers

External reviewer 1

DATE: 4.12.2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	x		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		3	See the comments in text.
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		4	The current status of development is not clear.
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		4	The blind text should be replaced by real samples.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x		4	Just one is missing.
Are the indexes correct?	x		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		3	There are some screen shoots not in English.
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		x	1	There are many missing.
Glossary present in the document?		x	1	Should be included.

Name: Andreas Schmidt

Partner: MOBA

External reviewer 2

DATE: 11.12.2017

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	x		Minor displacements in google docs. Page 21 blank? Figure on page 32 has graphic errors.
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		No specific tasks mentioned in sections? So not sure what the advance is and can only get description.
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x		
Are the indexes correct?		x	None match. Might be due to import in google docs?
Is the written English correct?	x		
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x		
Glossary present in the document?		x	Terminology is integrated, but might be useful to have separate glossary?

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Partner: SGI